

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****CONTAGION IN HIGH LEVELS OF BLOOD SUGAR OF LONG
DURATION**¹Obaidullah Qureshi, ²Iqra Aslam, ³Muhammad Ammar Ashraf¹Ghazi Khan Medical College D.G Khan²Shaheed Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Medical University³Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan**Abstract:**

All around the globe, the common health issue faced by people is Diabetes Mellitus. If diabetes is not managed, the working of B-cell and T-cell is influenced. As a result, susceptibility of bacterial attack enhances. Occasion of metabolic complexities in this disorder increases as the vulnerability of bacterial infections increases. The situations that endangers life can be retarded by managing the optimal glycaemia and awareness regarding this disorder. Through awareness, unhealthy state of mind can be managed. Seriousness of indications can be eliminated by proper selection of actual medication. Experts should be consulted if the situation is critical.

Keywords: *Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Opsonophagocytosis, Humoral, Bacteruria, Rhinocerebral mucormycosis,*

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Please cite this article in press Obaidullah Qureshi et al., *Contagion in High Levels of Blood Sugar of Long Duration.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Lack of insulin in the body causes the Diabetes Mellites (DM). It is a long-term disease. All over the globe, the number of individuals who are suffering with Diabetes Mellites (DM) are 347 million as reported by World Health Organization (WHO) [1]. According to prediction, in 2030, the seventh biggest reason that will lead to death is DM [2]. Vulnerability to bacterial and fungal infections increases, if this disorder is not managed. This vulnerability enhances when working of neutrophils, oxidant - antioxidant disparity, deficient opsonophagocytosis and T-lymphocytes becomes inefficient [3]. The assessment and elimination of bacterial infections is very hard. It is due to the fact that humoral immune reactions are weak. Diabetes Mellitus may become complexed due to enhanced vulnerability to bacterial infections. In some diabetic patients, some conditions are particular [4]. Further complications occur due to mucosal attachment with *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* and sensory and autonomic neuropathy. Possible reasons of infections in individuals with DM and spectrum of this disorder is illustrated in Table-1. For physicians, controlling the infections in diabetic patients is always a difficult task. Rules of controlling the disorder are as follows:

1) Awareness of diabetes associated diseases:

The situations that endangers life can be reduced through awareness regarding this disease and managing optimal glycaemia. To proper management, it is necessary to understand the types and seriousness of the disorder in individual with DM. Other problems that are related to this disease can be minimized by adopting precautionary measures such as suitable foot care [5]

2) Choice of antibiotics:

Medicines should be selected by considering the organism causing infections. As long as

the microbiological outcomes are confirmed, for proper treatment, actual broad-spectrum medicines should be used. For the reduction of related problems of disorder and death rate in individual with DM, in time apprehension of antibiotic resistance is required. Patients are admitted to hospitals with cytotoxic chemotherapy, broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, cystic fibrosis and mechanical ventilation. These patients are usually observed with *P. aeruginosa* infections. For different infections of bacteria, option of drugs is shown in Table – 2 [6]. Polymicrobial cover, particularly to lower anaerobes is very necessary to prevent skin and soft tissue infections, periodontitis with emphysematous cholecystitis and diabetic foot infections.

3) Glycaemic control:

During the course of infection, the necessity of insulin increases. For the management of glycaemia, insulin should be used first. The complexities related to infections increases due to bad management of glycaemia. So, insulin should be preferred which is an anabolic agent.

4) Source control:

For elimination of dangers of complexities and for proper management of glycaemia, it is necessary to manage source in the form of drainage.

When to Refer:

Any situation that is critical and can't be handled by physician, may be handed over to experts. In diabetes mellitus that complicate renal disability, diabetic foot, life endangering invasive *Mucor* mycosis and pregnancy, first concern should be given to referrals.

Table No 01: Disease spectrum with causative organism and salient features

Organ System	Spectrum of infections in population with DM	Likely causative organisms	Salient features
Respiratory system	Community acquired pneumonia Tuberculosis Influenza	Streptococcus pneumoniae Legionella Klebsiella pneumonia Staphylococcus aureus Mycobacterium tuberculosis H1N1	Fever Cough Sputum production Fever Cough Dyspnoea Pleural effusion Fever Sore throat Diarrhoea Respiratory distress
Genito-Urinary Tract	Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Perinephric abscess Bacterial cystitis Emphysematous Cystitis Fungal cystitis Emphysematous pyelonephritis	E. coli Enterobacter aerogenes E. coli Acinetobacter species Group B streptococci P. aeruginosa E. coli Enterobacter species Proteus Klebsiella Candida E. coli Enterobacter species Proteus Klebsiella	Fever Flank pains Fever Urinary frequency Fever Backache
Gastro-intestinal	Oral and Oesophageal candidiasis Emphysematous cholecystitis Liver abscess H. pylori infections	Clostridium perfringens E. coli Bacillus fragilis Klebsiella pneumonia Helicobacter pylori	Dysphagia Pain abdomen Fever Pain abdomen Diarrhoea Jaundice
Skin and soft tissue	Folliculitis Furunculosis Cellulitis Necrotising fasciitis Fournier's gangrene Invasive Rhinocerebral mucormycosis Malignant Otitis Externa Diabetic Foot	Group A streptococcus Staphylococcus aureus Streptococcus pneumoniae Streptococci Enterobacteriaceae E. coli Bacteroides sp. Staphylococci Streptococci Proteus Pseudomonas Clostridium perfringens Rhizopus Mucor species Pseudomonas aeruginosa Aspergillus species Group A streptococci Staphylococcus aureus Gram - negative rods Anaerobes	Skin rash, Swelling Redness Swelling of the limb Redness Black discoloration Bony erosion Pain in the ear Pus discharge Discoloration of the foot Loss of sensation

Iatrogenic and surgical site infections	Pulp infection Injection site abscess Catheter related peritonitis	Group A streptococci Staphylococcus aureus Gram - negative rods Group A streptococci Staphylococcus aureus Group A streptococci Staphylococcus aureus Candida	Induration at site of catheter insertion
Others	HIV Hepatitis B & C Endophthalmitis Periodontal disease Helminthic infections Ectoparasites	E. Coli Klebsiella sp. Anaerobes *Preventive role in type 1 diabetes	

Table No 02: Choice of drugs for various infectious.

Organism	Antibiotic first line		Second line	
	Oral	IV	Oral	IV
S. pneumonia		Penicillin Ampicillin	G/ Macrolides cefuroxime	Cefotaxime Ceftriaxone
Mycobacterium tuberculosis	Isoniazid Rifampicin Pyrazinamide Ethambutol		Moxifloxacin Levofloxacin Azithromycin	Kanamycin carbapenem
Legionella	Macrolides		Quinolones Tetracycline	
Klebsiella pneumoniae	Cefixime Cefdinir Cefpodoxime	Carbapenam Amikacin Cephalosporins 3rd generation (Ceftriaxone, Cefotaxime) & 4th generation (cefepime)		Tigecycline Polymyxin B Polymyxin E
Staphylococcus aureus	Amoxicillin	Penicillin G	Cefazolin Linezolid Doxycycline TMP-SMX	Vancomycin
E. coli		Carbapenams Amikacin Cephalosporins (Ceftriaxone, Cefotaxime, Cefipime) Piperacillin-tazobactam		
Acinetobacter species	Sulphamethoxazole-trimethoprim	Sulbactam Carbapenam Polymyxin E	Doxycycline	Amikacin Tigecyclin
Group Streptococcus	B	Benzathine penicillin G		Vancomycin
Group Streptococcus	A	Benzathine penicillin G	Cephalexin Cefadroxil	
Pseudomonas aeruginosa		Ceftazidime Cefipime Piperacillin-tazobactam Carbapenams	Quinolone	Amikacin
Rhizopus & Mucor	Amphotericin Liposomal Amphotericin B	B		Echinocandin

CONCLUSION:

There are many different forms of serious infections that are related to diabetes mellitus. Information regarding these infections should be provided to health care staff. The infection and related issues can be resolved and macro vascular complexities. Pneumococcal and influenza is usually vaccinated. The management of optimal glycaemia is important. This is helpful in proper management of infections. The problems related to disorder should be predicted earlier.

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